

Earnings Management, Audit Firm Size, and Audit Quality: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the relationship between earnings management, audit firm size, and audit quality. Using a literature review approach based on 71 scientific articles, four main discussions were identified. First, audit firm size has not yet become a commonly used topic for measuring audit quality. Second, publicly listed companies remain the dominant research objects, indicating opportunities for further studies on private companies. Third, audit quality measurement still largely relies on the Big 4 versus Non-Big 4 classification due to its simplicity. Fourth, earnings management measurement is generally approached from the company's perspective, while alternative measurements from the perspective of the audit firm as the auditor remain rarely explored. This study also has limitations, particularly the limited access to a broader range of articles. Future research is therefore expected to incorporate a larger number of studies and include article categories indexed in databases such as SCOPUS or SINTA.

KEYWORDS: Literature review, Earnings management, Audit firm size, Audit quality

I. INTRODUCTION

To date, companies continue to rely on professional accountants to provide audit opinions on financial statements so that external stakeholders can be assured that the information disclosed by firms is reliable (Handoyo & Febriani, 2025). Unfortunately, various major cases have arisen from problems related to audit opinions, such as those involving Enron Corp. and WorldCom Inc. After years of operation, Enron was proven to have concealed substantial debt from shareholders through cooperation with other entities, accounting fraud, and illegal lending practices. Similarly, WorldCom—once the second-largest telecommunications company in the United States under the leadership of Chief Executive Bernie Ebbers—was found to have engaged in aggressive earnings management to reduce costs and inflate revenues. Arthur Andersen, the audit firm responsible for both companies, was considered to have failed to reveal these scandals, thereby eroding investor confidence (Handley-Schachler & Li, 2006, as cited in (Widyaningsih et al., 2019).

Audit quality provides multiple perspectives for capital markets. High-quality audits reflect credibility and value, support investment decision-making, enhance transparency, and reduce information asymmetry (Riadi et al., 2025; Payamta et al., 2025). Audit quality is also frequently associated with fraud occurrence, although empirical findings remain mixed. Lubis et al., (2024) and Yousefi Nejad et al., (2024) argue that audit quality does not necessarily prevent fraud, whereas Riadi et al., (2025) contend that high-quality audits can reduce fraud risk and strengthen auditors' effectiveness in fraud prevention.

In addition, audit quality is closely related to earnings management. Prior studies indicate that audit quality serves as an effective governance mechanism for reducing earnings manipulation (Kusuma & Malau, 2023; Le, 2025; Amara et al., 2025). Beyond earnings management, audit quality is also associated with audit firm size. Some studies show that larger audit firms tend to deliver higher audit quality because they can charge higher audit fees and allocate more resources to audit engagements (Choi et al., 2010). However, other research suggests that audit firm size may no longer be a relevant determinant of audit quality (Zhang & Huang, 2025), particularly when auditors possess sufficient client-specific knowledge (Knapp, 1991; Johnson et al., 2002; Chi & Huang, 2004, as cited in Al-Thuneibat et al., 2011).

Based on the discussion above, the three variables—earnings management, audit firm size, and audit quality—appear to be interrelated, yet a clear conceptual mapping remains limited. Therefore, this study aims to further examine the relationships among these variables and to identify potential avenues for future research arising from existing research gaps.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW A. AUDIT FIRM SIZE

Audit firm size has long been recognized as a proxy for audit quality; however, it has not fully evolved into a comprehensive measurement framework, thereby limiting a broader understanding of audit quality. Since the works of DeAngelo (1981) and Dye (1993), Deep Pocket Theory has explained the relationship between audit firm size and audit quality. Large audit firms face higher litigation risk, possess greater resources, implement more efficient audit processes, and have stronger reputational incentives to maintain audit quality (see Zhang & Huang, 2025).

Audit firm size can be operationalized in several ways, including the total assets audited by the firm, the total audited sales of client companies (Zhang & Huang, 2025), the number of clients served, and the total audit fees earned (Choi et al., 2010).

B. EARNINGS MANAGEMENT

Earnings management occurs when managers intentionally use judgment in preparing financial statements and structuring transactions in ways that may mislead stakeholders regarding the firm's true economic condition (Kjærland et al., 2020a). Ronen and Yaari (2008), as cited in Siekelova et al., (2020) classify earnings management into three types. First, white earnings management, which uses accounting policy flexibility to signal expected future cash flows. Second, gray earnings management, which employs accounting discretion to maximize economic efficiency or managerial interests. Third, black earnings management, which involves deliberate misstatements or actions that reduce the relevance and reliability of financial reports.

Earnings management can be measured using various approaches. One method is the Eckel index, which compares profit over a given period with sales in a single period (Ghofir & Yusuf, 2020). Another widely used measure is discretionary accruals based on the Modified Jones model, calculated as the difference between total accruals and non-discretionary accruals (Saleh et al., 2020)

C. AUDIT QUALITY

Audit quality can be defined as the auditor's ability to detect and correct material misstatements in financial statements (Li & Liu, 2024, as cited in Amara, Bouzgarrou, et al., 2025). High-quality audits are produced when auditors are both independent and competent—capable of identifying errors and willing to report them (Hartono & Laksito, 2022). Moreover, audit quality is reflected in the auditor's commitment to prioritizing the public interest over managerial or personal interests when issuing audit reports (Sangadah, 2022).

Audit quality may be measured using several indicators, including classification based on audit firm size—namely Big Four versus non-Big Four audit firms (Nurrohman & Zulaikha, 2013)—and the issuance of going-concern versus non-going-concern audit opinions (Hartono & Laksito, 2022)

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive research design using a literature review approach, grounded in the post-positivist philosophical paradigm, which is used to examine phenomena in their natural context (Sugiyono, 2013, as cited in Saputra & Siregar, 2022). The study provides a comprehensive synthesis of prior research based on previously published scientific articles relevant to the topic under investigation. In this research, data analysis is not intended to test or reject hypotheses but rather to describe observed phenomena, which are not necessarily expressed in numerical or coefficient form (Saputra & Siregar, 2022).

The study initially identified 200 scientific articles. These articles were retrieved using the Publish or Perish (PoP) software and subsequently analyzed using VOSviewer for bibliometric mapping. The articles were sourced from Google and Google Scholar, focusing on topics related to audit quality, earnings management, and audit firm size. The keywords used in the search process were *"audit quality," "earnings management,"* and *"audit firm size."*

Article screening and analysis were conducted using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) approach, as illustrated in the following figure:

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IV. DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Relationships Among Variables

Based on Figure 1, two main discussions emerge. First, earnings management is associated with corporate governance mechanisms, particularly the audit committee and audit quality. The presence of an audit committee may reduce the risk of earnings management (Kjærland et al., 2020b), partly due to its routine participation in annual meetings (Handayani & Ibrani, 2020). However, in some cases, audit committees exist merely to comply with regulatory requirements issued by the Financial Services Authority, thereby limiting their effectiveness in constraining earnings management (Handayani & Ibrani, 2020). Second, earnings management is closely linked to audit quality. Audit quality reflects auditors' capabilities derived from education, experience, and professional training, enabling them to prepare reports in accordance with applicable standards and detect fraud in financial statements. Empirical evidence indicates that higher audit quality negatively affects earnings management (Kalbuana

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et al., 2022). Audit quality itself is influenced by multiple factors, including audit fees, which may enhance auditor independence (Soyemi et al., 2020)

The discussion above also suggests that audit firm size has received less scholarly attention compared with earnings management and audit quality. At least two reasons explain this limitation. First, measurement bias arises because audit firm size can be proxied in various ways, such as total firm assets, number of branches, total audited client assets, number of employees, and other indicators. Second, confidentiality constraints limit data availability. Information regarding audited client assets and staffing levels is often undisclosed by audit firms due to client confidentiality and competitive protection.

Figure 2. Classification by Company Sector

Figure 2 illustrates the industry sectors examined in prior studies. Approximately 34% (23 studies) focus on non-financial companies, whereas 13% (9 studies) examine financial and manufacturing sectors. This pattern indicates that research on earnings management, audit quality, and audit firm size predominantly relies on nonfinancial firms, partly because the financial sector is subject to stricter regulation (Gerged et al., 2023).

The figure also shows that most studies analyze publicly listed companies, making secondary data the primary information source. Nevertheless, private firms also present potential for earnings management because managers may still pursue profit-based incentives, highlighting an opportunity for future research.

Figure 3. Classification by Audit Quality Measurement

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Figure 3 indicates that 81% (22 studies) measure audit quality using the Big Four versus Non-Big Four classification, while alternative measures include return on equity (ROE), Likert-scale assessments, domestic Big Four classifications in China, and auditor specialization. The Big Four dummy variable assigns 1 if the firm is audited by a Big Four auditor and 0 otherwise (Kurniawati & Panggabean, 2020). Big Four auditors are often assumed to reduce expectation gaps, enhance credibility, and detect larger losses earlier (Hasan et al., 2020). Beyond these measures, audit quality may also be assessed using audit firm size, audit fees, audit tenure, industry specialization, and number of subsidiaries (Husain, 2020). Auditor specialization is particularly relevant because specialized auditors possess deeper knowledge of clients' industries, operations, and accounting regulations (Abba & Sadah, 2020). **Two key issues arise from Figure 3. First, reliance on the Big Four/Non-Big Four proxy—while simple—introduces measurement bias, implying that only Big Four auditors deliver high-quality audits. Second, the use of dummy variables oversimplifies measurement, suggesting the need for interval or Likert-scale-based indicators to capture audit quality more comprehensively.**

Figure 4. Classification by Earnings Management Measurement

Figure 4 shows that 74% (37 studies) measure earnings management using discretionary accruals, while 16% (8 studies) employ real earnings management (REM). Discretionary accruals are widely used because they capture managers' ability to influence reported earnings to obtain incentives (Dechow et al., 1995; Shuto, 2007, as cited in El Deeb & Ramadan, 2020). Such discretion is often not explicitly defined in contracts, enabling managerial opportunism (Siekelova et al., 2020) and selective disclosure of favorable or unfavorable information to capital markets (Saleh et al., 2020). In contrast, REM involves manipulating real business activities to manage reported earnings (Graham et al., 2005; Roychowdhury, 2006, as cited in Ghaleb et al., 2020).

These findings indicate two research gaps. First, earnings management is typically measured from the company perspective, relying on client financial data rather than the auditor's perspective. Second, measurement predominantly uses financial data, with limited incorporation of non-financial indicators, suggesting the need for broader methodological development.

Figure 5. Classification by Country

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Figure 5 states that 25% (16 studies) use Indonesia as the research object, while 13% examine eight companies in Jordan and Nigeria. Indonesia is frequently selected due to several factors, including increasing investment, talent development, and business model innovation (Sayidah et al., 2020), as well as the emergence of notable corporate scandals, such as those involving PT Hanson International, PT Garuda Indonesia in collaboration with PT Mahata Aero Teknologi (Andriani et al., 2021), PT Bank Lippo, Tbk (Arnas et al., 2021), PT Kimia Farma, PT Kereta Api Indonesia, and PT Waskita Karya, Tbk (Mukhtaruddin et al., 2022). In addition, Indonesia's service industry growth (Rijal et al., 2023). Additionally, Indonesia is among the few countries regulating mandatory audit rotation (Martani et al., 2021).

Nigeria is also considered a relevant country of study due to the limited attention given to accounting scandals that have contributed to the collapse of several banks, including Oceanic Bank, Savannah Bank, SocietyGeneral Bank, and Afribank Plc (Ugwu et al., 2020), as well as Cooperative and Commerce Bank (CCB), African Continental Bank (ACB), and Orient Bank (Ibrahim & Abdon, 2020). In addition, Nigeria's business environment dominated by conglomerates (Amahalu et al., 2020) and the challenges faced by professional managers in maintaining accountability (Yayangida et al., 2023).

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to examine the relationship among earnings management, audit firm size, and audit quality through a literature review approach based on 71 scientific articles. The findings generate four main discussions. First, audit firm size has not yet become a commonly used measure of audit quality, primarily due to measurement bias and data confidentiality, particularly regarding the number of clients and employees within audit firms. Second, publicly listed companies remain the dominant research objects, indicating significant opportunities for future studies focusing on private firms. Third, the measurement of audit quality still largely relies on the Big Four versus Non-Big Four classification because of its simplicity; however, this approach contains notable measurement limitations and bias. Fourth, earnings management is predominantly assessed from the company perspective, while alternative measurements from the audit firm's perspective as the auditor remain relatively unexplored.

This study is subject to limitations, particularly restricted access to a broader range of academic articles. Therefore, future research is encouraged to incorporate a larger body of literature and include studies indexed in recognized databases such as Scopus or SINTA.

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